

Effect of Compensation Structure and Distributive Justice on Employees' Job Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutions in Gombe State

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study is to examine the effect of Compensation Structure and Distributive Justice on Employee Job Satisfaction. Two research hypotheses were formulated from literature to capture the essence of this study. The research was conducted among teaching and non-teaching staff from two of the Gombe State owned Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) that is; Gombe State Polytechnic, Bajoga and College of Education, Billiri. Convenient sampling technic was used to reach out to the 250 respondents, derived out of the entire 673 staff of the two institutions based on Krejcie and Morgan sampling size table of 1970. Data was collected through the use of adapted structured questionnaire. The tool used for analyzing the descriptive statistics and reliability was the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23, while the SEM was aided by Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS) software, version 23. The study is influenced by the theoretical framework of Equity theory. Findings from the study indicated that, Distributive justice and Compensation structure were reported to have significant and negative relation with job satisfaction. These results suggest that Government should pay much emphasis to the compensation structure which has to do with their remuneration, allowances and to the larger extent, the welfare of the institutions' employees. The management of the institutions should be open and fair in duty offerings, equitable chances in carrier development which has to do with seminars, conferences, workshops and more so furtherance of education (higher degrees). In addition, there should be appropriate rules and regulations in order to have fairness of decision making.

Keywords: Distributive Justice, Compensation Structure, Job Satisfaction, and Gombe State.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of Job Satisfaction has been studied widely by many scholars, and still receiving considerable attentions. Employees' Job satisfaction plays a very important role in a workplace.

Employees that were happy in their jobs, tend to have a better quality of life than those who aren't. Organizations that keep their Employees happy often see a plethora of positive effects on their productivity, as satisfied employees tend to be committed, show a greater cooperation and reduced likelihood of quitting (Farrington & Lillah 2018). On the same vain, Employees that were highly satisfied, were reported to be more attributable with higher productivity, less absenteeism, having less stress, and the organization normally experiences lower staff turnover than those having unhappy employees (Chin, 2018; Arab & Atan, 2018).

Job satisfaction was considered as an effective approach to retain and attract potential employees and more also, an important mechanism toward enhancing employees' morale, enhance co-workers' relationship, promote creativity & innovation and encourages organizational citizenship behavior that influence organizational success. Intrinsic and Extrinsic influential factors, were argued to have received considerable attention among scholars in relation to Job

satisfaction (Mardanov, 2020). Others were; Distributive leadership (Torres, 2018), Trust and Information networks (Aziz *et al.*, 2021) and likewise, Compensation and Benefits (Le *et al.*, 2020). Although, all these indicators of job satisfaction such as; pay, working environment, welfare package, recognition, and inclusiveness in decision making were centered around organizational justice.

Organizational Justice represents an employee's perception of justice in a workplace, and the degree to which individuals believe that; the outcomes they received and the way in which they were treated by an organization is fair, equitable and in line with expected moral and ethical standards (Barau, 2018). A more detailed focus on job satisfaction shows that, employees may be satisfied with some aspects of the job, but not with others (Fennell, 2021). The degree of perceived fairness either pulls employees together or pushes them apart by either fostering inclusion or exclusion (Barau, 2018).

Studies in human resource management and organizational behavior have focused considerable attention to the concept of organizational justice due to its relationship with several work-related outcomes, such as; job performance, commitment, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), job satisfaction, perceived organizational support, and turnover (Arab & Atan, 2018). Human resources are an important factor in an organization.

Justice induces voluntary and proactive attitudes and actions for members of an organization, and has an important influence on the stability, maintenance, and performance of the organization (Yu *et al.*, 2019). Job dissatisfaction emanates from lack of justice. Lack of justice makes employees feel undervalued. A study among teachers revealed that, those working in the public sector were generally dissatisfied, specifically with distribution of benefits, procedures for running the institutions and interpersonal relationship (Farrington & Lillah 2018). Dissatisfaction leads to poor work quality and less efficient service delivery.

The promotion of organizational justice toward enhancing job satisfaction, should be the major concern of all organizations, if only they needed the best out of their employees. Although, there were studies on the relationship between organizational justice and job satisfaction in the prison service (Sembiring *et al.*, 2019), Banking, IT and manufacturing sectors (Karem *et al.*, 2019), the police (Qureshi *et al.*, 2020), but it was scanty on Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) of learning. As (HEIs) plays a crucial role in educational, technical, social and economic Wellbeing of a country, the role of their staff in the achievement of these purposes cannot be overemphasized, as both academic and Non-Academic staff play a crucial role in the operation of academic institutions. Thus, the need to have the best brains, who were adequately satisfied with their jobs to get the best result. However, these prompted the need to carefully study the effect of some components of Organizational justice in Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) of learning in Gombe State in relation to Job satisfaction.

To determine the effect of the relationship, the following hypotheses were stated:

Ho1: There is no significant and positive relationship between Compensation Structure and Employee Job Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutions in Gombe State.

Ho2: There is no significant and positive relationship between Distributive Justice and Employee Job Satisfaction in Higher Educational Institutions in Gombe State.

Concept of Employees' Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important work attitude for both staff and their employing institutions. Job satisfaction is the pleasurable or positive emotional feelings a worker has about his or her job experiences in relation to previous experiences, current expectations, or available alternatives. It is also 'the extent to which people like or dislike their jobs' (Lamond, *et al.*, 2017; Spector, 1997) Job satisfaction results when employees' appraisals of their job experiences fulfill their employment-related wants and needs and lead to a positive emotional states (Lambert *et al.*, 2020). Job satisfaction is associated with reduced work absenteeism, lower levels of job burnout, decreased turnover intent/turnout, increased support for educational programs, higher life satisfaction, greater commitment to the organization (Keena *et al.*, 2020), an increased likelihood of engaging in pro-social work behaviors (i.e., going above what is expected), greater creativity and support for organizational change and improved performance (Woldearegay, 2021).

Determinants of Job Satisfaction

The most popular dimension of job satisfaction is often the Herzberg's intrinsic and extrinsic job characteristics (Hauff *et al.*, 2015). The intrinsic factors are called the motivators while the extrinsic factors are the hygiene aspects (Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

Salary or pay: The first determinant of job satisfaction is the level of wages and compensation. The wage level has a direct effect on the level of income for individuals and hence affects their utility function. The jobs with better wages are probably characterized by higher security rates, job tenure and physical and mental health (Ezzat & Ehab 2018).

Numerous other studies identify pay and workloads as factors influencing teacher job satisfaction. Teachers feel satisfied with satisfactory and stable salaries, and because of poor salaries, many experience teachers have higher resignation tendency almost daily. Job security: This includes safety priority, job tenure and physical and mental health (Veretennik & Kianto 2020). Operating conditions: Teachers are often dissatisfied with their work environments, which are sometimes characterized by damaged and poor facilities.

The work itself or nature of the work: organizational context (policies, procedures, systems, and culture and climate). Individual characteristics (e.g. education level, ethnicity, immigrant status). Work-life balance: This is affected by excessive workloads, where staff may be compelled to work in the evenings, long hours, and on weekends (Zeki *et al.*, 2019). Extrinsic rewards: This includes pay, benefits, and professional growth (Matla & Xaba, 2020): Extrinsic rewards cause both job satisfaction and dissatisfaction for employees. Job satisfaction will be high due to comparatively good pay, pay equality, fair assignments, coworker relationship, adequate equipment, and reasonable physical and repetitive work. Intrinsic rewards: These include autonomy, responsibility, growth, recognition, and achievement.

Others lead to increased productivity and decreased turnover. Worker relations: The feelings of connection and belonging strengthen motivation. Being respected by supervisors and by other workers. Effective supervision: Supervisor cooperation (hygiene factor) refers to the supervisor behavior which helps the employees to demonstrate the skills, knowledge and attitudes collected from the training program (Le *et al.*, 2020). Job satisfaction leads to stronger job performance, increased organizational citizenship behavior, improved customer satisfaction, moderately reduced and decreased intention to leave or turnover (Chetty, 2018) and organizational commitment (Bibi *et al.*, 2019).

Organizational Justice

Organizational justice has been receiving considerable attention in an area of human resource management, organizational psychology and organizational behavior. It represents an employee's perception of justice in a workplace. It is defined as "the degree to which individuals believe that the outcomes they receive and the way in which they are treated by an organization are fair, equitable and in line with expected moral and ethical standards" (Barau, 2018). Perceived organizational justice refers to anyone's subjective perceptions of the fairness of allocations Zayer & Benabdelhadi (2020). Organizational justice influences organizational commitment, organizational citizenship, job satisfaction, and performance (Colquitt, 2001; Swalhi *et al.*, 2017).

Three types of justice perceptions were identified, these are; distributive, procedural, interactional (Interpersonal and informational justice). Distributive justice refers to the fairness of outcomes for individuals in comparison with what others received. Procedural justice refers to whether the decision-making processes ensure consistency and whether recipients of these decisions have the opportunity to influence the process. Accordingly, Interactive justice refers to the perceived quality relationship within the organizational hierarchy (Minibas-Poussard *et al.*, 2017). Interpersonal justice refers to whether one is treated with dignity and respect when decision processes and decisions themselves are implemented, while informational justice refers to the extent to which employees feel that they have adequate information as decisions were implemented.

Organizational justice has been researched widely in relation to subjectivity (Barau, 2018), decision making (Eberlin & Tatum, 2008), emotional exhaustion (Hur *et al.*, 2015), whistle blowing (Hur *et al.*, 2015), and cognitive outcomes (Katsumi *et al.*, 2019). The degree of perceived fairness either pulls employees together or pushes them apart by either fostering inclusion or exclusion. Employees expect just treatment from the organization and the leaders to which they devote their time and energy (Barau, 2018).

The concept of justice (i.e., fairness) is an important part of society. Organizational justice refers to the perception that the employing organization treats employees in a fair and just manner (Colquitt, 2001) (Lambert *et al.*, 2020). Justice is a glue that holds people together and allow them to work effectively, whereas injustice can pull them apart. Organizational justice/injustice is a major part of job resources because of its potential for supporting or hindering the motivation of employees to achieve goals and their awareness of learning and growth in the organization (Ren *et al.*, 2021). Employees retaliate against unjust work outcomes by engaging in sabotage behaviour that harms the organization and/or other employees. Indeed, aggrieved employees with perceptions of injustice can display retaliatory behavior in terms of reduced commitment and decreased productivity.

Perceived justice on the other hand, could increase the job satisfaction (Zahednezhad *et al.*, 2020). When the levels of perceived justice are high, staff will engage in positive attitudes and, increase productivity, cooperate with the organization, and adhere to the ethical and moral norms of the organization (Yu *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, if members were to perceive that the treatment they receive is unfair, they might experience lower drive to work, leave the organization or even show resistance to the organization (e.g., losses, illegal strikes, and leaks of confidential business

information due to frequent turnover) (Mylona & Mihail 2001). The four dominant dimensions of organizational justice are procedural justice, distributive justice, Interactive Justice and Compensation Structure (Colquitt *et al.*, 2001).

Compensation Structure

Compensation is the combination of all cash incentives and the mix of fringe benefits that an employee receives from a company and it constitutes an individual employee's total compensation (Ashraf, 2020). Compensation structure includes items such as retirement (pension and gratuity), health insurance, life insurance, disability insurance, paid leave, paid holidays, flexible scheduling, and educational assistance to name a few. These benefits bind an employee to the employing organization and result in a strong job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Compensation can be categorized as intrinsic or extrinsic, financial or non-financial and direct or indirect benefits, which influence job satisfaction and ultimately organizational commitment.

Evidently, compensation has an important link between the rewards a company offers and those individuals who are attracted to the compensation into working for the organization and those employees who will continue the work for the business (Devonish, 2018). Generous rewards and incentives tend to retain people because high rewards lead to enhanced job satisfaction, organizational commitment and company loyalty (Ashraf, 2020). Compensation structure can be classified into three types of pay: job-based pay, skill-based pay and performance or competency-based pay. The most common and traditional approach of compensation is referred to as job-based pay that is determined by the degree of difficulty, responsibility and relative value of a job, whereas skill-based pay is determined by the employee's skill and knowledge. Competency-based pay is a way of payment in which employees are paid for their demonstrated performance or competencies and is determined by the employees' output. Lack of job satisfaction and positive motivation in the workplace affects the spirit of organizational commitment, which is the central issue in business organizations and their future growth.

Distributive Justice

This refers to employees' perceived fairness about work outcomes. The performance outcomes include pay, performance rating, promotion, power sharing, prestige, and outcomes of dispute resolutions. Thus, employees experience distributive justice when they perceive that they are receiving sufficient return from social and economic resources (Fujimoto *et al.*, 2013); Barau, 2018). Distribution should be based on a transparent upholding of established criteria. It relates to the morality of the distribution of "burdens and benefits". Distributive justice is more salient in affecting the personal outcomes of an individual, such as satisfaction with payment.

Distributive justice is based on perceptions of equity rather than equality. Equality refers to all employees experiencing the same outcomes regardless of their efforts or contributions to the organization. In contrast, equity refers to the situation when a specific employee's outcomes depend on his or her efforts and contributions to the organization. According to the equity exchange principle, employees assess organizational outcomes based on individual inputs (i.e., contributions), comparing their inputs and outcomes relative to other employees to determine whether they are being treated fairly. In other words, distributive justice is based on the equity exchange principle. That is, people compare what they (and others) have done in exchange for what they (and others) have received in order to determine whether or not the outcomes are perceived as just (Ahmed & Alenezi 2023). The distribution will be just, when the most qualified and successful employee is promoted.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Source: Adapted from the work of Ashraf *et al.*, (2020), Dhaouadi & Sliti, 2020; Niehoff & Moorman, 1993)

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Compensation Structure and Job Satisfaction

Adeoye & Fields, (2014) investigated the relationship between compensation management and employees' job satisfaction in Nigeria's Insurance Sector. The instrument used in information gathering was questionnaire. In all, 250 questionnaires were administered to the employees of an insurance company, 213 were retrieved and 212 were found usable for response rate of 84.4%. The statistical analysis revealed that compensation management and employees' job

satisfaction are significantly correlated though weak and that compensation management have an impact on motivation and job satisfaction of employees’.

Kadarisman, (2019) analyze the influence of compensation, development, and supervision towards the performance of civil servants in the Government of Depok City. This research used Mixes Method. The quantitative design used explanatory survey, and data analysis used Structural Equations Modelling (SEM) and software Lisrel 8.72 version. It also used descriptive method, qualitative design, and purposive sampling to obtain a deep and thorough explanation. The result of the research is: showed that compensation is significantly influential at level 5% of mistakes toward the performance of civil servants at 0.61 percent. There are also indicators that make up the Compensation Variable which provide the biggest contribution here is the Indicator X5 by 0.86, which is about justice in giving bonuses. The policy of giving compensation is apparently able to increase the performance of the civil servants.

Distributive Justice and Job Satisfaction

Ghaderi *et al.*, (2023) examined the impact of distributive justice on employees’ organizational commitment (affective, continuance, and normative) on the employees’ job satisfaction. A total of 119 questionnaires were gathered from employees in one to five-star hotels in Tehran. The results show that, distributive justice has a strong relationship with job satisfaction. Similarly, between employees’ organizational commitment dimensions, only normative commitment has a meaningful impact on the employees’ job satisfaction. However, dissimilar to the previous studies. This indicates that, study of this nature could be replicated in Nigeria, by including all the dimensions of organizational justice.

Yu *et al.*, (2019) verify the effects of organizational justice on the performance of hotel enterprises. The data used in the empirical analysis were collected from Luxury hotel employees. A hierarchical regression analysis was used. The results showed that among sub-factors of organizational justice, distributive justice has the greatest effect on work engagement, and work engagement has an important effect on decreasing turnover intention.

Mylona & Mihail (2019) explores how employees’ performance in the public sector is affected by perceptions of organizational justice in terms of resource allocation (e.g., benefits and compensation). The responses received from a sample of 490 employees working for public organizations in Greece indicated that work performance is significantly and positively related not only to employees’ satisfaction with pay, but also to employees’ perceptions of distributive and procedural justice. Model suggests that the relationship between organizational justice (distributive and procedural) and work performance (work effort and work quality) is fully mediated by pay satisfaction. In particular, it is indicated that organizational justice is positively related with pay satisfaction. The study did not indicate the tool used in data collection for the study, but the study can be replicated to enhance the employees job satisfaction in the study area.

Equity Theory

According to Adams' Equity Theory (1960), there should be a balance between the amount of effort an employee that employee puts in and the results they receive in return. A worker's input-output ratio is compared to the ratios of other workers, and if the two are equal, equity is said to exist (Robbins & Coulter, 2005). The distributive justice theory of equity has been intensively examined during the last few decades (Yusof & Shamsuri 2006; Mefi & Nambei 2021) Rewards have been shown to improve employee satisfaction only when valued and seen as fair by the recipients (Durant *et al.*, 2006). To better understand the connection between a teacher's motivation and his or her impression of fair treatment, educators have turned to equity theory. Employees in higher education institutions, on the other hand, use equity theory to compare their own input/output ratios to those of another employee. Inputs in this context include the time, expertise, qualifications, and experience of the employee, as well as intangible human traits such as motivation and ambition, and interpersonal skills of the employees. Financial pay, perquisites (extra benefits), incentives, and work arrangements that are more flexible are some of the outcomes of the process. There are two ways that employees who see injustice can combat the problem: they can either adjust inputs and/or results directly (cognitive distortion) or they can leave the company altogether (Khan *et al.*, 2021). There are significant consequences for staff morale, efficiency, productivity, and turnover in higher education institutions.

Methodology and Data collection

The research design adopted for this study was quantitative survey design which aimed squarely, at the need to gain a deep understanding of an area that has previously received little attention. The population of the study consist of all the staff of Gombe State Polytechnic, Bajoga (GSP) and College of Education Billiri (COEB), both in Gombe State, Nigeria. However, based on the data collected, GSPB and COEB has a total number of 271 and 402 employees respectively. So therefore, the total population is 673 employees, out of which 250 respondents were selected as the sample size as recommended by Krejcie and Morgan Table of 1970, while convenient sampling technique was used to reach out to the respondents. Data was obtained with the aid of a structured questionnaire. While AMOS SEM Version 23 was used to analyzed the collected data. This technique used has become imperative due to the fact that, this study involves a structural model which serve as most suitable way to evaluate the fit of the proposed model (Hoyle, 1995).

Results Analysis

Figure 1: Measurement model of the entire construct after the re-specification was made.

Source: AMOS SEM Output Version 23.0 (2023)

Table: I Assessment of the fitness Indexes of the entire Constructs.

Name of category	Name on index	Index Value
Absolute fit	RMSEA	0.062
Absolute fit	GFI	0.941
Absolute fit	NFI	0.955
Incremental fit	CFI	0.975
Parsimonious fit	ChiSq/df	2.232

Source: AMOS Output, Version 23.0 (2023)

To ascertain the level of multicollinearity between and among the construct under study. Literature recommended that, for any correlated construct with a value higher than 85% (0.85), either of the two construct should be dropped, as ‘one is a mirror to the other’. Looking at the values in the measurement model, the highest and the least correlated values were 74% (0.74) and 41% (0.41) between DJ & CS, and DJ & JS respectively so therefore, there was no multicollinearity issue. Nevertheless, the model, based on its fit indexes as displayed in table I above, it is fit to be subjected into Structural modelling.

Figure II: Final Structural Model of the overall Variables

Source: AMOS SEM Output Version 23.0 (2023)

Table: II

Path relationship	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P. V.	Result
CS → JS	0.307	0.103	2.977	0.003	Rejected
DJ → JS	0.241	0.099	2.425	0.015	Rejected

Source: AMOS SEM Output Version 23.0 (2023)

The results of the hypotheses tested using CFA SEM path modelling, rejected both **Hypothesis I** ($\beta = 0.307$; CR= 2.977; P= 003) and likewise **Hypothesis II** ($\beta = 0.241$; CR= 2.425; P= 0.015). As anticipated, there is no significant and positive relations between Compensation structure and Distributive justice among the employees of the institutions under review, so therefore, the result rejected the null hypotheses, by implication accepted the alternate (there is a positive and significant relationship among the variables under study). This also mean that, the more unfavourable Compensation structure and Distributive justice are, the more employees become less satisfied. The result indicated too that, when CS

goes up by 1%, Job satisfaction increase by 31%. This simply mean that, all other variables held constant, unfavourable CS predict JS by 31%, which appeared in the hypotheses testing as significant in predicting JS.

Nevertheless, as the second null hypothesis was rejected too, this means that, Distributive justice positively and significantly influences Job satisfaction in Gombe state HEIs. As all other variables held constant, unfavourable DJ predict JS by 24%, which appeared in the hypotheses testing as significant in predicting JS.

On a general note, the value of R² for the entire contributions of the two (2) variables studied in relation to Job satisfaction is 20% (See Figure II). Although, this research has gotten 20% contributions on the dependent variable; Compensation structure and Distributive justice on the employees' job satisfaction in these institutions, as their contributions were 31% and 24% respectively. This suggest that, other researchers can as well look into other items of Organizational justice, or may expand the scope of the research to other Higher institutions of learning in the state, so as to ascertain the level, more than 20% to say, 100%.

Appendix I: Population of the study

S/N	Staff Category	Population of the study	
		GSPB	COEB
1	Management staff	07	07
2	Senior Non-Academic staff	18	83
3	Academic staff	78	103
4	Junior Non-Academic staff	168	209
	Sub-total	271	402

Source: Field Survey, 2023

NB: GSPB- Gombe State Polytechnic, Bajoga.

COEB- College of Education, Billiri

CONCLUSION

This paper, provides an overview of some of the influential factors that can predict job satisfaction in two selected higher institutions of learning in Gombe state. The paper tryaddresses issues related to employees' job satisfaction in the sector, being a crucial sector, any country should be proud to have developed, and sustained. As policies and initiatives of government in addressing this challenge in Nigeria and in Gombe state to be precise, tend not to have given a satisfactory result on issues related to staff of Higher institutions in the State. On the same vain, the result as indicated, signifies a negative relationship among the variables which clearly show that, the compensation structure and distributive justice in place demotivate the employees. Demotivation or unhappy employees result to problems such as; lower productivity, absenteeism and increases the chance of quitting.

Recommendation

Government should as a matter of urgency, come up with policies and programs that will contribute immensely to employees' job satisfaction, through creating sustainable compensation structure that is more attractive and beneficial to employees of these institutions. Management of these institutions should be demonstrating the elements of fairness in allocating duties/roles, chances for further studies, seminars, conferences and workshops should be equitably shared with fairness, if ad only if the satisfaction of the employees is to be looked into, other than allowing these valuable assets (staff) to be quitting and embracing other opportunities from other sectors or, moving overseas. It was out of negligence from the side of government/management that, most of these resourceful employees were found to be either redundant or into informal behaviors (such as; absenteeism, inability to display some elements of creativity or innovations) in their workplace, etc.

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